

OPPORTUNITIES FOR FORMING SPIRITUAL COMPETENCE IN HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. In this article, high school students learn about the content, opportunities, stages of formation of professional competence, qualities of professional competence, directions of professional competence, self-development through the textbooks "Individual developed work program", "Turkey" the development of spiritual competence, the spiritual competence presented in the "Education" textbooks, the spiritual competence of students-youth are discussed.

Key words: spirituality, competence, spiritual competence, professional competence, qualities of professional competence, formation of personal spirituality, "Education" textbooks, spiritual competence of students, self-development, value chain, basic competencies.

Enter. Development of an interactive system for diagnosing the development of students' moral competence with the help of information and communication technologies is gaining importance. In economically developed countries, it is necessary to acknowledge the creation of a set of qualities specific to the requirements of the present time in future specialists.

Today, it is important to organize spiritual and moral education processes in general education schools based on the effective application of the model of spiritual competence, by developing a sense of belonging to social and political situations in students. is enough. On the other hand, in the development of the moral competence of the graduates of the general education school, it is of particular importance to expand the forms of social manners specific to the requirements of the present time, to educate high moral qualities by establishing social sociability and competence in students.

The main part. In the period of new development of Uzbekistan, to increase the effectiveness and effectiveness of spiritual and educational work, to further expand their scope and scale, to strengthen the sense of belonging to the reforms being implemented in the hearts of young people, to work in the direction of propaganda and education. organization on a scientific basis, increasing the effectiveness of scientific and methodical research in this field, and introducing a permanent monitoring system aimed at strengthening the stability of the socio-spiritual environment is being paid great attention. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-80 of January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan" for 2022-2026, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 11, 2022 "2022 — To create the moral and moral image of our students in the Decree No. PF-134 on the approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2026 and other regulatory and legal documents related to this activity, serves to a certain extent the implementation of tasks such as the development of spiritual competence in them.

To date, attention is paid to the reforms implemented in the education system in our country based on a special approach. Therefore, today in general education institutions, all conditions are being created for the development of students in all aspects. Also, one of the most important tasks of our research is to implement the possibilities of forming spiritual competence in students of 10-11th grade of general educational institutions. After all, in the 10-11th grades, students learn their mutual communicative relations, solidarity, friendship, mutual support, rules of etiquette, as well as social etiquette norms

in differentiation relationships. , it is of particular importance that they express their spiritual and positive attitudes in the process of socialization. At the time when 16-17-year-old students are starting an independent life, it is necessary to guide them correctly, to find their place in life, and to form active citizenship positions. It is desirable to develop the ability to put into practice the knowledge acquired by them. More than 60% of our country's population is made up of our youth. Taking this into account, we are all equally responsible for the education of our students and their development as morally perfect people. It is necessary to increase the activity of parents along with pedagogues-teachers in the development of spiritually mature young people. We use the rich scientific heritage of our ancestors to achieve this goal. The spiritual heritage they left us has been serving us for centuries, and is helping our young people to become well-rounded individuals. In addition, we also pay special attention to the development of spiritual competence within the framework of our research topic. Youth reforms have been raised to the level of state policy. On January 19, 2021, under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the head of our state said at a video selector meeting on the issues of fundamental improvement of the system of spiritual and educational affairs and strengthening the cooperation of state and public organizations in this regard: If the body of society is the economy, then its soul and spirit is spirituality. As we decide to build a new Uzbekistan, we rely on two strong pillars. The first is a strong economy based on market principles. The second is the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values. strongly emphasized that "spirituality".

There are various interpretations to describe the concept of "Spirituality", in the explanatory dictionary "Spirituality: Basic Concepts": "Spirituality (Arabic, meaning, set of meanings) - with material life A generalized definition is given in the form of "a social phenomenon that always goes side by side, is an integral part of the life of a person, people and society".

Competence is a term that expresses the level of a person in a certain field, having knowledge that allows one to make a correct judgment about a certain situation. Competence is a complex set of personal characteristics and conditions, which embodies knowledge, skills and experience in a certain field. Competence allows a person to express an opinion on certain issues, to participate in the development of certain decisions or to make decisions on his own. In modern science, professional competence is widely used in researches related to scientific, management, pedagogical, didactic, methodical, socio-psychological competence. Management competence is determined by the presence of knowledge and skills related to this field, practical experience in management activities. "Competence - knowledge, suitability for the profession, competence, experience, instilling in leadership activities."

In the 60s and 70s of the last century, a new direction of research in education appeared. The word "competence" comes from the Latin meaning "to achieve, to do correctly". In other words, it is the subject's personal ability to set a goal and achieve it, to effectively organize external and internal reserves, to solve certain professional issues of the subject.

In general, the terms "competence" and "competence" are not analyzed in the same way by pedagogues. Competence-oriented education The general meaning of the term "competency" proposed by the American linguist M. Homeke (1956) from the University of Massachusetts was formed. At the symposium held in Bern (1996) under the program of the Council of Europe, it is noted that "competence" is included among concepts such as ability and skill.

Although the content of the concepts "competence" and "competence" are aimed at the same goal, they differ in essence. These concepts entered the use of pedagogy and psychology in the 60s of the last century, and appeared in the 70s and widely entered the theory and practice of professional training of students. Competence-oriented education was proposed by American linguist N. Chomsky (1965, University of Massachusetts). The general meaning of the term "competence" was formed. At the symposium held in Bern (1966) under the program of the Council of Europe, the concept of "competence" was included among concepts such as "training", "competence" - "ability", "skill". In the Balonia Declaration (1999) of the Ministry of Education of European countries, the competent approach was recognized as the conceptual basis of educational reforms. Based on the above-mentioned points, today students and young people are given all kinds of conditions and benefits for acquiring their professions at a high level in the future and using them in practice.

According to B. D. Elkonin: "competence means instilling knowledge, suitability for the profession, competence, experience, and responsibility in the field of leadership. To be a master of one's field means to know the secrets of one's field in depth"¹.

Competence is deep knowledge of a field, awareness of many things, used to describe the final results of education in one's specialty, while some scientists used it to express various characteristics of a developed person. According to research, the solution of pedagogical tasks goes back to the trinity of "thinking, acting and thinking". The teacher's model of professional competence is reflected on the basis of the compatibility of his theoretical and practical training level.

For today's young pedagogue, to go to foreign countries and exchange experience or to invite foreign specialists to educational institutions of Uzbekistan for the purpose of exchange of experience, all this prepares the ground for improving the professional competence of today's modern teacher. It should be noted that the term "spiritual competence" is not mentioned separately in the scientific-pedagogical literature related to the existing field. However, it is necessary to clarify the essence of the concept of "spiritual competence" in connection with the research subject. A special hypothesis was put forward that the answer to the solution of the problem can be determined by analyzing the basic competencies.

Through the textbook "Education" intended for high school students, we identified the following moral competence (Fig. 1):

Figure 1. Spiritual competence presented in the "Education" textbook (10th grade).

¹ Эльконин Б.Д. «Понятие компетентности с позиции развивающего обучения» М. 2002 г.

The role of social institutes in instilling the mentioned spiritual and moral qualities in students is of particular importance. All public organizations are working tirelessly to further increase the activity of social institutions. Our goal is to identify the factors of socialization of students and increase the scope of opportunities for their development. 16-17-year-old students should be occupied by instilling creative ideas into their minds, preventing any destructive ideas from coming into their minds. In order to fill the ideological gap, we need to teach them social etiquette. Spiritually mature people cannot be deceived by any spiritual threats, destructive ideas, or false information. A morally perfect person is a person who has his own position in any situation and can make the right decision after looking at the most optimal option. We also aim to train such mature individuals in the process of socialization for our society.

During our observations, we studied the "Education" textbooks intended for high school students. The spiritual competence given in the textbooks is included in the topics. In it, it is explained through the methods of pedagogical influence, and examples are given by example. Pupils and young people who mastered the BKM given through this textbook and methodical manuals will become a perfect person with their place and position in the society as a well-rounded person in the future, will serve the interests of the Motherland and the people.

Summary. Spiritual issues are covered in Islamic sources in a wide way. The use of these resources in the formation of spiritual competence among students increases the effectiveness of our expected results. The issue of spirituality is always the most important aspect of our agenda. That is why, first of all, it is necessary to raise the spirituality of young people, to fill the spiritual gap in them, in every way. When we talk about Islamic manners, we are talking about the manners that are considered to be the best among all the world's wealth, the beautiful and exemplary manners that parents cannot give their children as a gift. The idea of Islamic manners derived from divine sources is closely related to divine teachings, goals, and ideals. The main idea of etiquette is to ensure that the human race achieves the happiness of two worlds. A Muslim man lives in harmony, cooperation and good relations with all beings in this world with his manners. And in the world of the hereafter, he will enjoy the reward of his manners. In order to understand this truth, it is enough to thoroughly understand the content of the verses of the Holy Qur'an about the desire and will of God to create man.

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